

REFORM OF THE BUDGETARY DISCIPLINE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION AND THE ROLE OF THE COURT OF JUSTICE

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Abstract

On the 13th December 2011, a series of legislative measures came into force that the European Commission qualified as the “most complete strengthening of the economic governance in the European Union and the Euro area since the setting in motion of the Economic and Monetary Union”. The so-called Six Pack is made up of: three Regulations that reform and strengthen the two pre-existing Regulations of the Stability and Growth pact; two Regulations that create a new procedure for avoiding excessive macro-economic imbalances in the Euro zone; and a Directive that fixes a common minimum in terms of budgetary policy that should exist in the internal financial-legal legislations of the Member States. This study analyses the reforms that have been carried out, in order to determine the implications for the members States of the EU and the role of the Commission, the Council and the Court of Justice in enforcing budgetary discipline.

Key words: Six Pack; Stability and Growth Pact; budgetary discipline; excessive deficit procedure; Programmes for Stability and Convergence; Court of Justice.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Within the framework of that which is included in the art. 104 C of the Treaty of the European Union of 1992 (current art. 126 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, from here onwards, TFEU), a process was started, at a European and national level, that was designed to contain the public deficit and debt of the Member States. The States that aspired to become members of the Economic and Monetary Union (hereinafter, EMU) should fulfil four convergence criteria (art. 109 J section 1 of the TEU), of which one of them demands that the sustainability of the government financial position. This criterion will be fulfilled when the member state does not surpass the limitations related to the public deficit and debt included in the art. 104 C of the TEU, mentioned above. The numeric values of reference to this end are specified in art. 1 of the Protocol N° 12 on the procedure applicable in the case of excessive deficit, annexed to the Treaty, according to which the States should not have a deficit higher than 3% of the GDP, nor a public debt higher than 60% of the GDP. These criteria of budgetary discipline do not constitute a mere access toll, but that the Member States should subsequently fulfil after the period of incorporation. The directives of the Treaty in this matter were developed by means of the approval in 1997 of the Stability and Growth Pact of the European Union¹.

The Stability and Growth Pact of the European Union (hereinafter, SGP) is made up of two parts: one which is preventive (that aims to strengthen the permanence of the budgetary positions and the coordination of the economic policies – Regulation N° 1466/1997, of 7 July 1997, on the strengthening of the surveillance of budgetary positions and the surveillance and coordination of economic policies) and one which is corrective (through which it is aimed to speed up and clarify the excessive deficit procedure – Regulation N° 1467/1997, on speeding up and clarifying the implementation of the excessive deficit procedure).

The SGP has been the object of two reforms. The first of them in 2005, following France and Germany's non-compliance with their public deficit undertakings: 3% of GDP. This first reform introduced a certain flexibilisation in the obligations fixed by the original SGP². The second reform in 2011, aimed to reinforce the European

¹ Resolution of the European Council on the Stability and Growth Pact. Amsterdam, 17 June 1997 (Official Journal C 236, 02/08/1997).

² On the one hand, COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) N° 1055/2005, of 27 June 2005, amending Regulation (EC) No 1466/97 on the strengthening of the surveillance of budgetary positions and the surveillance and coordination of economic policies. On the other hand, COUNCIL REGULATION (EC) N°.

budgetary discipline within the context marked by the economic crisis, the sovereign-debt crisis of some of the Member States, and the generalised non-compliance of the levels of deficit and public debt fixed in the Treaty. The reality has made it patently clear that the SGP is an inefficient mechanism for avoiding the existence of excessive deficit and public debt. The majority of the Member States find themselves immersed in a process of excessive deficit, without this leading to the application of the punitive measure included in the Regulation on speeding up and clarifying the implementation of the excessive deficit procedure.

This situation has led to the Commission implementing a legislative package (the so-called six pack) that, in the words of the Commission itself, contains “*the most comprehensive reinforcement of economic governance in the EU and the euro area since the launch of the Economic and Monetary Union*”³.

As follows, we will analyse in a detailed way the two Regulations of the Six Pack that reform the pre-existing Stability and Growth Pact and the Regulation N°. 1173/2011, on the effective enforcement of the budgetary surveillance in the euro area. The purpose of this study is to determine the implications of the reforms for the member States of the EU and the Court of Justice’s role in the control of budgetary discipline.

2. REFORM OF THE REGULATIONS OF THE STABILITY AND GROWTH PACT

2.1. Reform of the preventive aspect of the Stability and Growth Pact

The text of the Regulation on Surveillance 2011 contains new relevant aspects with regard to the Regulation on Surveillance in its version given by the Regulation N°. 1055/2005. As follows we will highlight the most significant ones:

First of all, the Regulation aims, in general terms, **to strengthen the surveillance made of the Member States**. Specifically, the European institutions should ratify the conformity and coherence of the figures presented by the States regarding the framework of budgetary coordination of the EU. To achieve this objective various specific measures were taken: i) to link in a more direct way the Stability and

1056/2005, of 27 June 2005, amending Regulation (EC) N°.1467/97 on speeding up and clarifying the implementation of the excessive deficit procedure.

³ EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *EU economic governance: the Commission delivers a comprehensive package of legislative measures*, IP/10/1199, 29/09/2010, Brussels.

Convergence Programmes with the decisions in budgetary matters that are adopted at an internal level. Furthermore, the Stability and Convergence Programmes have to be presented and analysed prior to adopting fundamental decisions with respect to the national budgets for the next few years; ii) to increase the approach by the States at an internal level of the policies approved by mutual agreement at a EU level; iii) to intensify the role of the Commission as a key organ in the procedure of the strengthened surveillance, especially in everything related to the assessment of the specific situations of the Member States, even by means of the carrying out of in situ missions⁴.

As a central mechanism for connecting this series of measures tending to a strengthening of the surveillance is the **European semester for the coordination of the economic policies**. It is established in accordance with that which is stated in art. 121(2) of the TFEU⁵. The European semester, regulated in art. 2 of the Regulation on Surveillance of 2011, is a period of six months (from January to June) during which time two types of actions are carried out. The first type of action aims to determine the main challenges to be faced both by the EU as well as by the area of the euro, and to offer strategic orientations about the policies to adopt. The second types of actions search for the surveillance of the budgetary and structural policies of the States. This surveillance is based on the Stability and Convergence Programme and on the national Programmes of Reform presented in April by the States. During the month of May, the programmes are evaluated by the Commission, which issues its recommendations. The recommendations are discussed and approved by the European Council in the month of June. This second phase of the European semester aims to detect and correct, during the period of preparation of the main national budgetary decisions, the possible incoherencies and imbalances that appear.

Once the European semester is concluded, what could be called the national semester begins, in which the States should take internal decisions in matters of economic and budgetary policies, following the guidelines fixed in the recommendation of the European semester⁶.

⁴ Recital (12) of the Regulation on Surveillance 2011.

⁵ Art. 121(2) of the TFEU states that “*The Council shall, on a recommendation from the Commission, formulate a draft for the broad guidelines of the economic policies of the Member States and of the Union, and shall report its findings to the European Council*”.

⁶ The so-called *Two Pack* stabilises new obligations for the Member States during the national semester. In particular, art. 6(1) of Regulation N°. 473/2013, of 21 May 2013, on common provisions for monitoring and assessing draft budgetary plans and ensuring the correction of excessive deficit of the Member States in the euro area, introduces an obligation for Member States to submit their draft budgetary plans to the Commission at the same time each year (by 15 October). The Commission shall adopt an opinion on the draft budgetary plan as soon as possible. If the Commission identifies particularly

The non adoption of the measures by the State against the orientations received could lead to three types of interventions: the issuing of new recommendations with a view to the adoption of specific measures; the approval of a warning from the Commission in conformity with that which is established in the art. 121(4) of the TFEU⁷; or the application of the measures established in the Regulation for the Excessive Deficit Procedure and in the new Regulation N°. 1176/2011, related to the prevention and correction of macro-economic imbalances.

The second new aspect introduced by the Regulation on Surveillance 2011 is the express reference to the need of presenting **Programmes of Stability or Convergence based on the most probable or most prudent macro-budgetary framework**⁸. Furthermore, if significant divergences exist between the chosen macro-budgetary framework and the forecasts of the Commission, it is necessary that such differences are duly justified. This rule refers to the principle of prudence, which has been included in a general way in art. 4 of the Directive N°. 2011/85/EU of the Council, of 8 November 2011, on requirements for budgetary frameworks of the Member States.

Thirdly, the reform of the preventative aspect of the SGP adds a third basic principle for the surveillance of the budgetary policies of the Member States: **the principle of prudent fiscal policy**⁹. The original preventive arm of the SGP, and in the

serious non-compliance of the SGP, the Commission shall request the submission of a revised draft budgetary plan (art. 7(2) of Regulation N°. 473/2013).

⁷ Art. 121(4) of the TFEU states that “*Where it is established, under the procedure referred to in paragraph 3, that the economic policies of a Member State are not consistent with the broad guidelines referred to in paragraph 2 or that they risk jeopardising the proper functioning of economic and monetary union, the Commission may address a warning to the Member State concerned. The Council, on a recommendation from the Commission, may address the necessary recommendations to the Member State concerned. The Council may, on a proposal from the Commission, decide to make its recommendations public*”.

⁸ In its turn, the information presented should be compared with the most up-to-date information of the Commission, and where appropriate with those of other independent organisations (art. 3.2 bis of the Regulations on Surveillance of 2011).

⁹ This principle establishes the fact that the growth of annual expenditure must not exceed a *prudent average percentage* in relation to the growth of GDP (art. 5 of the Regulation on Surveillance of 2011). Under this premise, the Commission and the Council will assess if the trajectory of public expenditure of a State adapts to the following conditions: “a) in the case of the Member States that *have reached the medium-term budgetary objective*, [that] the annual growth of the expenditure does not exceed *a rate of potential growth of the GDP* in the medium-term that serves as a reference, unless the excess is compensated with discretionary measure related to the revenues; b) in the case of the Member States who *have not yet reached the medium-term budgetary objective* [that] the annual growth of the expenditure does not exceed *a lower rate than the rate of potential growth of the GDP* in the medium-term that serves as a reference, unless the excess is compensated with discretionary measure related to the revenues. Therefore, if the State fulfils the medium-term budgetary objective, its expenditure should be below a rate of potential growth of GDP; however, if it does not fulfil this objective, its expenditure should be at a

same way that of the SGP after the reform of 2005, is based on two principles that should be complied with by all the Member States of the EU. The first of these is the obligation of achieving their respective budgetary objectives in the medium term. The second principle refers to the adjustment path to achieve the budgetary objective in the cases in which these are not complied with; specifically, it fixes the obligation of reducing the deficit by 0.5% of their annual GDP.

The principle of prudent fiscal policy constitutes the first direct limitation of the volume of expenditure regulated in the SGP. The other two pre-existing objectives in the preventative phase do not make any specific reference to the aspects of the budget, revenues or expenditure, but to a budgetary situation of balance and tending towards the same. In a similar way, in the corrective arm of the SGP (art. 126 of the TFEU, and the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure), the criteria of the deficit and the public debt fixed as parameters for the opening of the excessive deficit procedure does not either make any reference to the obligations for the reduction of expenditure¹⁰.

However, the principle of prudent fiscal policy doesn't signify a complete limitation of public expenditure. This principle grants a certain margin of manoeuvre to the national budgetary Legislator so that it implements measures of increase of revenues through which, despite the increase of expenditure above a rate of potential growth of GDP, is able to fulfil the principle of prudent fiscal policy.

In terms of the **enforcement of the surveillance**, art. 6 of the Regulation of the Surveillance of 2011 establishes the measures that can be adopted by the Commission and Council in the case of significant deviations with respect to the adjustment path towards the medium-term budgetary objective. The rule determines that the non-compliance by the State empowers the Commission to intervene, and if this non-compliance persists or is especially serious, the possibility is opened up for the Commission to issue a recommendation to the Council so that this adopts measures based on art. 121(4) of the TFEU.

Furthermore, if, within a maximum period of 5 months, the State does not take suitable measures for the compliance of the recommendations given by the Council, the Commission will recommend to the Council to adopt a decision, by qualified majority, indicating the fact that no effective measure has been taken.

lower rate than the rate of potential growth of the GDP. The fundamental aim of this new principle is to ensure that the extraordinary revenues are not destined to cover expenses, but to reduce the public debt.

¹⁰ Only after the infringement of the deficit criterion or the debt criterion, the Commission shall prepare a report, which shall also take into account whether the government deficit exceeds government investment expenditure (art. 126(3) of the TFEU).

If the Council does not adopt the decision about the recommendation of the Commission in which it states that effective measures have not been taken, and the Member State continues to not adopt suitable measures, the Commission, once one month has passed since its first recommendation, will recommend to the Council that it adopts the decision in which it states that no effective measure has been taken. The decision will be considered adopted by the Council unless this decides, with a *simple majority*, to reject the recommendation of the Commission within a period of ten days.

The actions described so far, basically the formulation of warnings and recommendations, can be accompanied by **corrective measures**. These constitute the first punitive interventions adopted in the preventive arm of the SGP; only applicable to the States of the EMU; and they take on the form of a deposit generator of interests of an amount equivalent to 0.2% of the GDP of the State. This deposit should be constituted after the proposal of the Commission, except if the Council, by *qualified majority*, establishes the contrary within ten days¹¹. These sanctions will be analysed in detail during the study of the new Regulation N°. 1173/2011 on the effective enforcement of the budgetary surveillance of the euro area.

Once the changes introduced have been noted down, we should carry out some appraisals. First of all, despite the establishment of a new principle and the fixing of objective criteria, numerical in character, so as to assess the existence of serious deviations of the objective of medium-term budgetary stability, the surveillance carried out by the European institutions continues to have an important discretionary component. In this sense, when the Commission and the Council assess the possible deviation of the medium-term budgetary objective or the non-compliance of the adjustment path for reaching the medium-term budgetary objective, they take into consideration different factors of the economic and budgetary situation of the State examined. As established in article 5 of the Regulation on Surveillance of 2011, a general assessment will be carried out in which the following aspects will be analysed: the state of the public debt and the risk of its global sustainability; the carrying out of adjustments most accentuated in times of boom or more limited adjustments if there are adverse times for the economy; and in particular the unexpected revenues and the unexpected drops in revenues will also be taken into consideration. Due to the assessment of the particular circumstance of each State, even if it is one of the new objectives of the SGP, the surveillance can become a casuistic question, reducing its egalitarian application with respect to the all the Member States. We cannot avoid the fact that the first reform of the SGP in 2005 was produced after its unequal application among the Member States; especially, the

¹¹ Art. 4 of the Regulation N°. 1173/2011, on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance in the euro area, regulates this measure.

fact of not initiating the excessive deficit procedure in relation to France and Germany after their respective non-compliances of the criteria fixed in art. 126(2) of the TFEU and the Regulation N°. 1467/97, related to the speeding-up and clarification the implementation of the Excessive Deficit Procedure¹².

The second appreciation is related to the system of inverse vote. With a general character, in the framework of the SGP, the Commission has the competence of the initiative of the procedure and the Council approves the measure in a definitive way. It happens this way, for example, in the start of the excessive deficit procedure (regulated in art. 126 of the TFEU). However, in the Regulations that make up *Six Pack*, for some measures, such as the two analysed and others we will see later on, the system of inverse vote has been introduced. By means of the inverse vote the recommendation made by the Commission about the non-adoption of any effective measure by the Member State, or the decision of the Commission about the constitution of the deposit with interest, will be taken except if the Council pronounces itself against the announcement of the Commission within a period of ten days, in the first measure by simple majority and in the second by qualified majority.

In terms of the effectiveness of the inverse vote, this system constitutes a relative advance in terms of the endorsement of the surveillance and corrective measures of the SGP, in terms of the fact that it provides certain automaticity to the decisions of the Commission. Nevertheless, the automaticity is only partial, as the Council will be able to decide to reject the proposal, for which it only needs to achieve a qualified majority, not unanimity. Moreover, the mechanism of inverse vote is only established for the adoption of certain decisions (such as the application of sanctions both in the preventive arm as well as the corrective arm), but not for all. In this way, for example, the key decision of opening the excessive deficit procedure continues to be adopted by the system of traditional vote¹³.

Before concluding the analysis of the Regulation on Surveillance of 2011, we should point out that this contains a new section, Section 3 *bis*. In this, it includes, among other aspects, the new **principle of statistical independence** (art. 10 of the Regulation on Surveillance). The independence of the national statistical authorities is a central element for carrying out the surveillance, insofar as the statistical authorities are those charged with elaborating and controlling the information presented in the

¹² The unequal application of the procedure led to the intervention of the Court of Justice (*Case C-27/04 Commission v. Council* (Judgment of 13 July 2004)).

¹³ In order to introduce a modification in the voting system for the opening of an excessive deficit procedure, it would be necessary to reform the TFEU. Art. 126(6) of the TFEU expressly states that the Council is the institution in charge of opening the procedure, and the Commission has the power to make recommendations about the opening (Art. 126(5) of the TFEU).

Programmes of Stability and Convergence. Specifically, the statistical authorities should determine the existing levels of deficit and public debt in application of the criteria of the European System of National and Regional Accounts (hereinafter, ESA – 95)¹⁴. The reliability of the statistical data is a crucial element. So much so, that it is in this way that the manipulation of the statistics can lead to the application of sanctions to the States¹⁵.

2.2. Reform of the corrective aspect of the Stability and Growth Pact

The Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure of 2011, introduced the following changes: To determine exactly the concept of “**substantial and continued reduction**” of the public debt towards the limit of 60% of GDP. The art. 2 of the Regulation of Excessive Deficit Procedure of 2011 establishes that a State fulfils the criterion of public debt if, in the last three years, it has carried out a reduction in the distance with respect to the value of reference of a percentage of the order of a twentieth part a year. Furthermore, based on art. 2 of the Regulation, it is considered that the debt is also fulfilled “*if the budgetary forecast of the Commission indicates that the reduction of the differential demanded is produced in the period of three years that comprise the two years following the last year regarding which figures are available* For a member State which is the object of an excessive deficit procedure of the 8th November 2011 and during the three years as of the correction of the excessive deficit, it will be considered that the requirement corresponding to the criteria of the debt has been complied with if the Member State in question makes sufficient progress towards its compliance, in accordance with the evaluation effected in the ruling adopted by the Council about its programme of stability and convergence”. As can be seen, the criterion for the reduction in the public debt (in a substantial and continued way) is a strict principle, but it is subsequently flexibilised, leaving an important margin of manoeuvre for the States to carry out a reduction in public debt.

Furthermore, the non-compliance of this value of deficit reduction doesn't necessarily entail the opening of the excessive deficit procedure. The declaration of excessive deficit is based on a report produced by the Commission (art. 126(3) of the

¹⁴ In order to know the public deficit and debt levels for compliance with limits established on the above-mentioned Regulations, Member States must submit their accounts in accordance with the Regulation (CE) N°. 2223/1996 approving the European System of Accounts (ESA–95); and as of 1 September 2014, in accordance with Regulation (EU) N°. 549/2013 (ESA – 2010).

¹⁵ These new category of sanctions is established in Regulation N° 1173/2011, on the effective enforcement of the budgetary surveillance in the euro area.

TFEU¹⁶), and for the production of the report the Commission analyses a wide range of factors, that the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure of 2011 qualifies as “pertinent factors”. These factors are included in sections 3, 4 and 5 of the art. 2 of the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure of 2011. The Commission highlights among the factors to take into account: the evolution of the public debt; a very low nominal growth that impedes the reduction of the public debt; factors linked to the risk in the structure of the public debt; the level of indebtedness of the private sector; and the possible implicit liabilities, such as those derived from the ageing of the population¹⁷.

With regard to the **carrying out of the procedure**, once the existence of the excessive deficit has been verified, the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure of 2011 tries to make this more agile. However, the analyses of the different phases of the procedure could lead us to conclude that the excessive deficit procedure maintains important similitude with the procedure in force up until the reform of 2011. The existence of “pertinent factors” could entail the approval by the Council of successive recommendations, revised recommendations, warnings and revised warnings, which delay the procedure and paralyse the intermediary stages. If excessively wide adjournments are produced, the credibility of the corrective value of the excessive deficit procedure will be little. For this reason, if a strict application is not carried out of the new shorter periods, it is possible that the new procedure ends up suffering from the same deficiencies of the previous excessive deficit procedure. This last became, to certain extent, a prolongation of the preventive arm, by constituting a second action plan for the reduction of the excessive deficit, without managing to apply the strictly sanctioning measures.

With regard to the sanctions, along with the original sanctions applicable in the final phase of the excessive deficit procedure (regulated in the arts. 6 and 12 of the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure of 2001) **new financial sanctions** are introduced that will be applied in the previous phase of the procedure and with a gradual focus. Specifically, after the declaration of the excessive deficit with respect to a State, an interest-free deposit will be constituted to the value of 0.2% of the GDP¹⁸. This

¹⁶ Art. 126(3) states that “If a Member State does not fulfil the requirements under one or both of these criteria, the Commission shall prepare a report. The report of the Commission shall also take into account whether the government deficit exceeds government investment expenditure and take into account all other relevant factors, including the medium-term economic and budgetary position of the Member State”.

¹⁷ EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the European council, the council, the European central bank, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. Enhancing economic policy coordination for stability, growth and jobs – Tools for stronger EU economic governance*, COM (2010), 367/2, 30.6.2010, Brussels, page 5.

¹⁸ EUROPEAN COMMISSION, “*Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the*

deposit will become a fine in those cases in which the initial recommendations for correcting the excessive debt are not complied with¹⁹.

Faced with these changes we should put forward various considerations. The Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure does not introduce sanctions of distinct natures. The Commission, in its Communication of the 30th June 2010²⁰, indicated a series of sanctions and incentives complementary to the use of deposits of fines, that was finally not included of the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure of 2011 nor in the Regulation N°. 1173/2011, on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance in the euro area. The Commission described this series of new measures as a “*tool box*” which it was possible to resort to depending on the specific circumstances of each State. Within this series of measures could be found the application of *reductions in the programmes of expenditure of the EU* with respect to the Member State immerses in an excessive deficit procedure²¹.

The aim of the Commission of introducing new sanctions (based on art. 136 of the TFEU) has only been partially carried out, as the reductions in European aid were not introduced. These constituted the main new feature of the initial proposals and one of the most feasible alternatives to the realization of deposits that can be turned into fines by the States, the effectiveness of this last mechanism being more than questioned. During the practical application of these interest-free deposits that can be turned into fine²² would not only aggravate the already poor state of the budgetary situation of the

European council, the council, the European central bank, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. Enhancing economic policy coordination for stability, growth and jobs – Tools for stronger EU economic governance”, COM (2010) 367/2, 30.6.2010, Brussels, page 9.

¹⁹ These sanctions are regulated in the new Regulation N°. 1173/2011, on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance in the euro area, and its approval by the Commission and the Council will be carried out by means of a system of inverse vote. Therefore, the decision of the Commission that obliges the constitution of the interest-free deposit will be considered to be adopted unless, by qualified majority, it is decided to reject the recommendation of the Commission within a period of ten days.

²⁰ EUROPEAN COMMISSION, *Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the European council, the council, the European central bank, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions. Enhancing economic policy coordination for stability, growth and jobs – Tools for stronger EU economic governance*, COM (2010) 367/2, 30.6.2010, Brussels.

²¹ Similarly, art. 4 of the Regulation N°. 1084/2006, of 11 July 2006 establishing a Cohesion Fund, states that if a Member State has not taken effective action in response to a Council recommendation made under Article 104(7) of the Treaty (*art. 126(7) of the TFEU*), the Council may decide to suspend either the totality or part of the commitments from the Fund for the Member State concerned with effect from 1 January of the year following the decision to suspend. This situation almost was found with regard to Hungary. COUNCIL, *Council implementing decision suspending commitments from the Cohesion Fund for Hungary with effect from 1 January 2013*, 2012/156/EU, of 13 March 2012, Brussels.

²² How GROSS notes, the rest of the corrective actions from the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure don not have the same importance or legal force. GROSS, Daniel, “Towards a credible

non-complying State. For this reason, its efficiency as a corrective measure of the situation is very low, given that the aim of re-establishing the budgetary stability would be even more complex to achieve once the fine is applied.

To sum up, one of the main aims of this reform was to provide the SGP with new corrective mechanisms, and this aim has finally not been achieved. The doctrine points out how the introduction and maintenance of financial sanctions (that have been shown to be inoperative) is the results of the impossibility of introducing other types of sanctions whose application would require the modification of the Treaty. This is the case of the political sanctions, as is the loss of vote in the heart of the Council²³.

In terms of the system of inverse vote, as we have already mentioned with regard to the new sanctions of the preventive aspect of the SGP, this constitutes an advance in its execution, to the extent that it provides a certain automaticity to the decision of the Commission. However, the automaticity is only partial, because the Council can decide to reject the proposal, for which it is only necessary to reach a qualified majority.

3. APPROVAL OF THE REGULATION N°. 1173/2011, ON THE EFFECTIVE ENFORCEMENT OF THE BUDGETARY SURVEILLANCE IN THE EURO AREA

The Regulation No. 1173/2011, on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance in the euro area (hereinafter Regulation on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance) regulates the **new financial sanctions** applicable both in the preventive arm, as well as in the corrective arm of the SGP. Thus, the art. 1 of the quoted Regulation determines its aim and field of application making an allusion to the “preventive arm” and to the “corrective arm” of the SGP. As follows, the Regulation, in its art. 2, defines what is understood by each of these two components: the preventive arm is the Regulation on Surveillance; while the corrective arm is the art. 126 of the TFEU and the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure.

In terms of the configuration of the sanctions applicable, this is covered in chapter III for the preventive arm, and in chapter IV for the corrective arm.

excessive deficit procedure”, *European Economic and Monetary Union: The Institutional Framework*, Centre of European Law, The Hague, Kluwer Law International, 1997, pages 245 - 246.

²³ RUFFERT, Matthias, “The European Debt Crisis and European Union Law”, *Common Market Law Review*, Vol. 48, (6), December 2011, page 1803.

In the preventive phase, the sanctions establish if the State does not adopt any measure in response to the recommendation of the Council regulated in art. 6.2 of the Regulation on Surveillance. This recommendation is the one which the Council enforces when it appreciates a significant deviation compared with the adjustment path towards the objective of budgetary stability. In the corrective phase, the sanctioning measures of the new Regulation are applied in two senses: i) after the declaration by the Council of the existence of excessive deficit (art. 126.6 of the TFEU) in a State that constituted a deposit with interests in front of the Commission in accordance with art. 4 of the Regulation on the effective enforcement of the budgetary surveillance; ii) if the Commission has detected an especially serious non-compliance of the obligations of the budgetary policy established in the SGP.

Therefore, both in the preventive as well as the corrector arm, the sanctions are established in the initial phases of the procedure, this being the main difference between the new financial sanctions in the Regulation on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance and the traditional financial sanctions included in the Regulation on the Excessive Deficit Procedure.

The sanctions have the same nature in both components. Both are money deposits that, in the case of the corrective component, can become fines. The difference can be found in the fact that the deposit of the preventive component will generate interests, while the deposit of the corrective component will be without interest. The amount of the deposit is the same in both situations (0.2% of the GDP of the State, corresponding to the preceding exercise).

The voting system for approving the new sanctions, as we already mentioned on analysing the reform of the two original Regulations of the SGP, is that of the inverse vote. The decisions of the Commission related to the constitution of the deposit (both in the preventive and in the corrective arms) and to the conversion of the deposit into a fine (in the corrective arm) will be considered to be adopted unless the Council decides to reject, by qualified majority, within a period of ten days, the recommendations of the Commission. Therefore, the Council continues to take the final and definitive decision about the approval of the sanctions. And, what's more, in both cases it could even modify the initial recommendations of the Commission and adopt the modified text as part of its own decision. This last option alters, in some sense, the competence of the Commission of the initiative of the procedures carried out within the framework of the SGP.

The second new feature introduced by the Regulation on effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance, is the creation (in its Chapter V) of a new category of sanctions, the **sanctions for the manipulation of statistics**. The Council, on the basis

of a recommendation of the Commission, will be able to decide the imposition of a fine to a Member State that by wilful misconduct or gross negligence distorts figures related to deficit and to the debt applicable with a view to arts. 121 or 126 of the TFEU or the protocol about the excessive deficit procedure attached to the TEU and the TFUE.

The introduction of these types of sanctions constitutes one step more in a long process carried out by European institutions for strengthening the reliability and the correction of the figures presented by the Member States.

However, the strengthening process has not brought to an end the deficiencies in the transformation of information within the framework of the SGP and the European authorities consider inconclusive the harmonisation of the elaboration and notification of statistical data in budgetary matters. For this reason, in 2011 two new measures were carried out: the directive was approved about the requirements applicable in the budgetary frameworks of the Member States, and sanctioning measures were established, in the Regulation about the effective enforcement of the budgetary surveillance, for those States that by wilful misconduct or gross negligence do not comply with their statistical obligations.

The Commission is the institution charged with carrying out all the necessary investigations for proving the existence of distortions of the statistical data. It will analyse all the information presented by the Member State, it will be able to require new information and will even be able to make in situ inspections. The Commission will have access to the accounts of all the public organisms at a central, regional and local level and of the social security of the State analysed²⁴. Once the Commission has completed its actions, and after providing the Member State with the opportunity of being heard in relation to the object of the investigation, it will present its proposal to the Council. This proposal should be based on facts about which the Member State has been able to make comments. The Council will be the institution charged with imposing the fine, based on the recommendation formulated by the Commission.

The Regulation about the effective enforcement of the budgetary surveillance specifies the fact that the rights of defence of the Member State should be respected in all cases. Under this premise, and given the marked jurisdictional character of the procedure, the Regulation establishes the possibility that the Member State lodges an appeal in front of the Court of Justice against the decision of the Council to impose the

²⁴ Art. 8(3) of the Regulation on the effective enforcement of budgetary surveillance determines that *“If the law of the Member State concerned requires prior judicial authorisation for on-site inspections, the Commission shall make the necessary applications”*.

fine. The participation of the Court of Justice in an established process in the heart of the SGP constitutes a significantly new element.

Frequently, due to the generalised non-compliance of the rules included in the SGP, doubts have arrived about the function that the Court of Justice should adopt in this matter. The Court of Justice is the institution charged with ensuring the compliance of the dispositions established in the Treaty, including the section regarding the EMU. However, art. 126 of the TFEU, in its section 10, excludes the action of the Court of Justice (through the *action for failure to fulfil obligations*) with regard to the implementation of the rule included in sections 1 to 9 of art.126 of the TFEU²⁵, this being the exclusive competence of the Council to ensure the correct application of the European budgetary discipline²⁶.

In this way, the function carried out by the Court of Justice in the development of the system of the Union in the “federal” sense (sustaining the legislative competence, or forcing the Council or the Commission to act) is found to be limited with regard to matters of budgetary discipline by the TFEU itself, that closes the procedural mechanism of the *action for failure to fulfil obligations* for these cases²⁷, foreseen in arts. 258 to 260 of the TFEU. The Court of Justice has to observe the action or omission of the Council, and only intervene in those cases (such as Case C-27/04, Commission versus the Council of 13th July 2004) in which it should ensure the institutional balance between the Commission and the Council. In these types of pronouncements, the Court of Justice should avoid analysing the material aspects of the SGP, as well as the nature of the non-compliances of the Member States or the suitability of the measures adopted by these.

Despite these procedural limitations, the Court can overrule the decisions adopted by the Council or Commission in accordance with paragraphs 6 to 9 of art. 126

²⁵ Art. 126(10) of the TFEU states that “*The rights to bring actions provided for in Articles 258 and 259 may not be exercised within the framework of paragraphs 1 to 9 of this Article*”. This article does not leave any doubt: The Court of Justice can not intervene through the procedures set out in articles 258 a 260 with respect to paragraphs 1 to 9 of art. 126 of the TFEU. These paragraphs regulate the obligation of the Member States to avoid excessive general government deficits and the obligation to comply with the Council recommendation in case of existence of an excessive deficit procedure. Therefore, the Commission or a Member State may not be brought an action for failure to fulfil obligations against a Member State that has failed to fulfil its obligations under art. 126 (1-9) of the TFEU.

²⁶ This exclusive competence of the Council has been criticised. See, among others, GROSS, Daniel, “Towards a credible excessive deficit procedure”, *European Economic and Monetary Union: The Institutional Framework*, page 241.

²⁷ The *proceedings for failure to fulfil an obligation* are the “*ultima ratio*” for ensuring compliance with the EU law. These proceedings may be brought by the Commission or by a Member State against a Member State, which has not complied with EU law.

of the TFEU, given that this passive competence, the result of the *action for annulment* (regulated in art. 263 of the TFEU²⁸), is not affected by the exclusion of art. 126(10) of the TFEU. However, this passive competence of the Court of Justice in itself limited²⁹, is even more biased by another fact: most of the actions of the Commission and Council throughout the excessive deficit procedure are carried out by means of recommendations and reports, acts that are expressly excluded from the control of the Court of Justice by art. 263 of the TFEU, which establishes that “*the Court of Justice of the European Union will control the legality of the legislative actions, the actions of the Council, of the Commission and of the European Central Bank that are not recommendations or reports (...)*”.

Finally, it is worth pointing out the hardly probable but possible option³⁰, that a national court, facing a case that would require the application of art. 126 of the TFEU, would address the Court of Justice so that it would interpret the rule (though a *preliminary ruling of interpretation*). After the response of the Court of Justice, the national judge would resolve the specific case.

In conclusion, the text itself of the Treaty clearly states the will of its writers to reserve for the Council, the competence of surveillance of the economic and budgetary policies of the States, and to leave in the hands of the Commission the initiative of the procedure. Article 126 of the TFEU closes the possibility that the Court of Justice directly knows these questions and reduces the possibilities that a strict and independent application is effected of the excessive deficit procedure.

²⁸ The *action for annulment* enables the Court to review the legality of legislative acts, of acts of the Council, of the Commission and of the European Central Bank, other than recommendations and opinions, and of acts of the European Parliament and of the European Council intended to produce legal effects vis-à-vis third parties.

²⁹ As ITALIANER points out, the Court of Justice loses its active competences (to interpret the criteria of paragraph 2 art. 126 of the TFEU and to establish corrective actions in case of infringement), but retains the passive, or indirect, competences. However, this second type of competences is limited. ITALIANER, Alexander, “The Excessive deficit procedure: A legal Description”, *European Monetary Union: The institutional Framework*, ed. Centre of European Law, The Hague, Kluwer Law International, 1997, page 226 and following.

³⁰ In order to make a reference for a preliminary ruling under Article 126 of the TFEU, it would be necessary a case already underway to a national Court. Given the specific character of budgetary discipline, it is difficult that an ordinary Court would analyse this topic; generally its management remains with Constitutional Courts. Some of the European Constitutional Courts don’t refer questions to the Court of Justice for a preliminary ruling, due to their jurisdictional limitations (restricted to a review of the constitutionality of laws). Such is the case of the German Constitutional Court, the Spanish Constitutional Court or the Italian Constitutional Court. However, the Constitutional Courts of some Member States (such as the Belgian Constitutional Court or the Austrian Constitutional Court) refer questions to the Court of Justice for a preliminary ruling, and eventually they could also refer a preliminary ruling seeking an interpretation of Article 126 of the TFEU.

Nevertheless, this new competence attributed to the Court of Justice by the Regulation of the effective enforcement of the budgetary surveillance opens up the possibility that the Court of Justice pronounces itself on aspects related to the deficit and public debt of the Member States. We will have to wait to check if, on resolving the potential appeal related to distortions of the statistics, the Court of Justice enters in to analyse material aspects of the budgetary discipline or if, on the contrary, it limits itself to checking that the actions of the European institutions, on imposing the fines, doesn't contravene the right of defence of the Member State sanctioned³¹

³¹ This second option is more consistent with the position adopted by the Court of Justice so far, not ruling about material aspects of budgetary discipline. At the same time, more legal dispositions confer new competences to the Court of Justice. Thus, art. 8 of the Treaty on Stability, Coordination and Governance in the Economic and Monetary Union (hereinafter TSCG) establishes the Court of Justice ability to review a State's compliance with the obligation of incorporate the golden rule "*through provisions of binding force and permanent character, preferably constitutional, or otherwise guaranteed to be fully respected and adhered to throughout the national budgetary processes*" (art. 2 of the TSCG). However, how FERRERES points out "the task that the TSCG entrust the ECJ with is not the one you would expect, to determine whether states comply with the golden rule, but rather a more indirect one, to check whether States have incorporated the golden rule in their constitutions". FERRERES COMELLA, Victor, "Amending the National Constitutions to Save the Euro: Is This the Right Strategy?", *Texas International Law Journal*, Vol. 48, (3), Spring 2013, page 236.

In this way, the TSCG does not give the Court of Justice specific competence as regards material aspects of the budgetary discipline.